

SOCIAL MATURITY OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

Dr. A. C. Lal Kumar* & Dr. M. Muthamizhselvan**

* Assistant Professor, G.E.T College of Education, Paradarami, Gudiyattam,
Vellore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Pedagogical Sciences, Tamilnadu Teachers
Education University, Karapakkam, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Social Maturity is the ability to function in an appropriate responsible manner. As adolescence is the age for an individual to express mature behavior. Social Maturity is an essential aspect for the individual as well as society. The present study was designed to investigate the social maturity of higher secondary students. For this purpose a total sample of 260 higher secondary students studying in 12th standard was taken on purposive basis from the schools of vellore district in Tamilnadu. Out of which 139 were male and 121 were female. In order to collect the data Social Maturity scale by Nalini Rao's were administered on the participants. Thus obtained data was analyzed using means, S.D's, 't'-test and F test. The results of analysis showed no significant contribution of social maturity towards gender, locality of institution, mode of management, group taught, medium of instruction, parental qualification, parental occupation and type of family.

Introduction:

The social maturity has various aspects of social abilities as self-sufficiency, occupational activities, communication, self- direction and social participation. Raj, M. defines social maturity as the level of social skills and awareness that an individual has achieved relative to particular norms related to an age group. It is a measure of the development competence of an individual with regard to interpersonal relations, behavior appropriateness, social problem solving and judgment. Every child is unique in itself and has its own pace of growth and development. As the child grows up, his emotions and social functioning changes and continuous till adolescence. Adolescence is that critical period of human development during which rapid biological, psychological and social changes takes place. This period marks the end of childhood and sets the foundation of maturity.

Social Maturity:

Social Maturity is a personal commitment each individual must make as the attitude that will influence his/her daily lives. Individuals can opt for the socially immature attitude of self-centeredness or they can opt for the socially mature attitude of genuine concern for the total well-being of each other. The very informal atmosphere of self-help groups where the individuals discuss and share their problems and their achievements with each other within the framework of caring and sharing without the fear of being exploited (Dilts, 1982) [2]. Ryff (1998) [8] proposes that some factors of well-being in particular self-acceptance, environmental mastery, and purpose in life are highly correlated with self-esteem. According to Major, Cooper, Richards and Zubek (1998) [9] self-esteem may be thought of as a core resource that contributes to resilient personality, and a person with a resilient personality has a positive view of him or her, a sense of control and an optimistic outlook on the future. Levi (1987) defined well-being as a dynamic state of mind characterized by a reasonable amount of harmony between an individual's abilities, needs, expectations and environmental demands. Social maturity is a term commonly used in two ways, with reference to the behavior that conforms to the standards and expectations of the adults and secondly, with reference to the behavior that is appropriate to the age of the individual under observation. Thus, the social maturation permits more detailed perception of the social environment which helps adolescents to influence the social circumstances and develop stable patterns of social behaviour (Bretsch, 1952) [11].

Methodology:

Normative survey method was followed. The present study is based on correlation method where the dependent variable is factors affecting social maturity where the independent variable is social maturity.

Sample:

The sample consists of 260 of higher secondary students selected from the schools of Vellore district. Out of which 139 were male and 121 were female. The sample was collected by using multistage random sampling technique

Tool:

Self-designed socio-demographic questionnaire was used to study the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents. Social maturity of the respondents was assessed by using Rao's Social Maturity scale developed by Nalini Rao's.

Statement of the Problem:

The problem chosen for the study may be stated as “Social Maturity of higher secondary students.

Statistical Techniques Used:

The investigator used the statistical techniques, Mean, Standard Deviation ‘t’ test and ‘F’ test to accept or reject hypotheses.

Operational Definitions of Key Term Used:

Social maturity means acceptance of a person or how a person is accepted in the society. It is characterized by the individual’s ability to establish social relations independently with different social groups of the society. Social maturity in this study has been taken as an aggregated countenance involving self-confidence, self-direction, social-feeling, productivity and social and human values. A composite score on human adequacy-personal, interpersonal and social- constitute a construct called social maturity.

Description of the Tool:

The items were scored by a five point scale. Namely strongly agree, a score of 5 is given, for agree a score of 4 is given, for neutral a score of 3 is given, for disagree a score of 2 is given and for strongly disagree a score of 1 is awarded. Higher score represent the high social maturity. The maximum social maturity score is $90 \times 5 = 450$ marks, and minimum social maturity score is $90 \times 1 = 90$ marks.

Objectives of the Study:

The following objectives have been formulated by the investigator for the present study,

- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between Male and Female higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between Rural and Urban higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between the sub samples of mode of management of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between the sub samples of group of taught of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between medium of English and Tamil of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between the sub samples of parental qualification of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between the sub samples of parental occupation of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ To find out if there exists any significant difference between nuclear and joint family of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.

Hypotheses of the Study:

The following hypotheses have been formulated by the investigator for the present study,

- ✓ There is no significant difference between Male and Female higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the sub samples of mode of management of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the sub samples of group of taught of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between medium of English and Tamil of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the sub samples of parental qualification of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the sub samples of parental occupation of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family of higher secondary students with respect to their social maturity.

Level of Significance:

The research workers chose several arbitrary standards for the convenience of interpreting the data. These arbitrary standards are called level of significance. For the present investigation the investigator has used 0.05 level as the significance to test the various hypotheses.

Differential Analysis Social Maturity:

Gender and Social Maturity:

Table 1: ‘t’ test between Mean Scores of Male and Female Higher Secondary Student towards Social Maturity

Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
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Male	139	295.37	58.16	0.336	NS
Female	121	297.95	66.00		

It is evident from the Table: 1; the calculated 't' value is 0.336, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their Social Maturity.

Locality of Institution and Social Maturity:

Table 2: 't' test between Mean Scores of Rural And Urban Higher Secondary Student towards Social Maturity

Locality of Institution	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	134	295.83	63.08	0.199	NS
Urban	126	297.36	60.70		

It is evident from the Table: 2; the calculated 't' value is 0.199, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their Social Maturity.

Mode of Management and Social Maturity:

Table 3: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Mode of management with Respect to their Social Maturity

Mode of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LOS
Between Groups	4574.33	2287.16	2	0.596	NS
Within Groups	985501.12	3834.63	257		
Total	990075.46		259		

It is evident from the Table: 3; the calculated 'F' value is 0.596, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of mode of management with respect to their Social Maturity of higher secondary students.

Group of Taught and Social Maturity:

Table 4: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Group of Taught with Respect to their Social Maturity

Group of Taught	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LOS
Between Groups	851.88	425.94	2	0.111	NS
Within Groups	989223.58	3849.119	257		
Total	990075.46		259		

It is evident from the Table: 4; the calculated 'F' value is 0.111, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Group of Taught with respect to their Social Maturity of higher secondary students.

Medium of Instruction and Social Maturity:

Table 5: 't' test between Mean Scores of English and Tamil Higher Secondary Student towards Social Maturity

Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
English	134	291.35	63.02	0.707	NS
Tamil	126	302.13	60.28		

It is evident from the Table: 5; the calculated 't' value is 0.707, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between English and Tamil higher secondary students with respect to their Social Maturity.

Parental Qualification and Social Maturity:

Table 6: 't' test between Mean Scores of School education and college education of parental qualification towards Social Maturity

Parental Qualification	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
School Education	149	291.98	63.88	1.389	NS
College Education	111	302.73	58.67		

It is evident from the Table: 6; the calculated 't' value is 1.389, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between school education and college education higher secondary students with respect to their Social Maturity.

Parental Occupation and Social Maturity:

Table 7: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Parental Occupation with Respect to their Social Maturity

Parental Occupation	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LOS
Between Groups	4629.66	2314.83	2	0.604	NS

Within Groups	985445.80	3834.41	257		
Total	990075.46		259		

It is evident from the Table: 7; the calculated 'F' value is 0.604, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Parental Occupation with respect to their Social Maturity of higher secondary students.

Type of Family and Social Maturity:

Table 8: 't' test between Mean Scores of Nuclear and Joint type of family towards Social Maturity

Type of Family	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Nuclear	122	296.87	63.24	0.073	NS
Joint	138	296.31	60.77		

It is evident from the Table: 8; the calculated 't' value is 0.073, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between nuclear and joint family with respect to their Social Maturity.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Male and Female higher secondary students with respect to social maturity.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Rural and Urban locality of institution of higher secondary students with respect to social maturity.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among the sub-sample of mode of management with respect to social maturity of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between group of taught of higher secondary students with respect to social maturity.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between English and Tamil medium of higher secondary students with respect to social maturity.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is a significant difference among the sub-sample of Parental qualification with respect to social maturity of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is a significant difference among the sub-sample of Parental occupation with respect to social maturity of higher secondary students.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between nuclear and joint type of family with respect to social maturity.

References:

1. Best John W, Khan James V. Research in Education, Tenth Edition, New Delhi. Prentice Hall of India Private Ltd, 2008.
2. Garrett Henry, Wood worth R S. Statistics in Psychology and Education, Surjeet Publications Ltd, New Delhi, 2008.
3. Greenberg E, Josselson R, Knerr C, Knerr B. The Measurement and Structure of Psycho-Social Maturity. Journal of Youth and Adolescence, 1995; 4:127-143.
4. Guilford JP. Fundamental Statistics in Psychology and Education New York, Mc Graw Hill Book Company Inc, 1956.
5. Lohithakshan P M. Dictionary of Education. A Practical Approach. New Delhi: Kanishika Publishers & Distributions, 2007.
6. Lokesh Koul. Methodology of Educational Research (2nd Ed) New Delhi, Vikas Publishing house Pvt. Ltd.,
7. Mangal S K. Advanced Educational Psychology (2nd Ed.). New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd, 2008.
8. Mangal S K. Essentials of Educational Psychology. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd, 2008.
9. Raj M. Encyclopaedia Dictionary of Psychology and Education. New Delhi: Anmol Publications, 1996.